

Would you like to contribute a blog post?

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Do you have experience as a women in STEMM academic leadership? Or have you started an initiative for women in STEMM that you would like to share with our readership?

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One of our intentions in launching this blog series is to provide a platform to share the collective knowledge of women interested or engaged in STEMM academic leadership. We hope that some of you – our readers – will be interested in joining us to help other women to be successful in achieving and maintaining their leadership goals and to have the highest probability of long-term success. We envision two types of contributions that would be based on interviews:

Sharing leadership experiences. We think that our readers would be interested to know how women became academic leaders, what the most and least enjoyable aspects of leadership are, what systemic changes could benefit women in STEMM academics, etc.

Initiatives for women in STEMM academics. We think our readers would be interested to learn about such initiatives, how they started, what they have accomplished, what future is envisioned for them, etc. Our first interview with Diane Rigos on the Epistimi initiative was recently [published](#).

For both of these types on contributions, we would provide potential contributors with a set of standard questions that could be answered in writing or in an oral interview with one of us (which we would transcribe). We would also work with the interview subjects on a short introduction and up to 3 concluding questions that would be intended to stimulate further thought, discussion, and action by our readers. We would edit the draft text for clarity and consistency, but the interview subjects would have final approval on the text before it is posted.

If you would be interested in participating in an interview, please contact us at: epistimiblog@gmail.com.

If there is there a relevant topic that you have particular insight into, this blog series might be a good opportunity to share your insights with our readers. We would be happy to discuss ideas for topics with potential contributors.

In closing, here are a few questions to stimulate further thought, discussion, and action:

- What would you like to contribute to this blog series?
- Whose contribution would you most like to see in this blog series? (Please forward this post to her or send your suggestion to us at epistimiblog@gmail.com.)
- What topic(s) would you most like to read about in this blog series?